

YasudaK Photon Model Based on Frequency Energy Flows

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Abstract

The YasudaK Photon Model proposes a novel representation of the photon as a structure defined by energy flows in helicoidal rotations. This document formalizes the model, detailing its foundational principles and visual framework.

1 Introduction

Photons are traditionally conceptualized as quantum packets of electromagnetic radiation. The YasudaK model introduces a structural approach, suggesting that photons consist of energy flows rotating helicoidally in opposite directions, stabilized by a central axis composed of Gluon Balls. This document describes the structural and dynamic aspects of the model.

2 Model Description

The YasudaK Photon Model is characterized by the following principles:

2.1 Energy Flows

- The model consists of **16 energy flows** arranged around a central axis.

- These flows are **helical** in nature, with alternating rotational directions.
- The flows are distributed symmetrically, creating a balanced and stable structure.

2.2 Rotational Directions

- **Red flows:** Represent **clockwise rotations**.
- **Blue flows:** Represent **counterclockwise rotations**.
- Opposing rotations ensure the dynamic equilibrium of the photon.

2.3 Central Axis

- The central axis is composed of **Gluon Balls**.
- Gluon Balls stabilize and direct the opposing energy flows.
- This axis acts as the core of the photon, anchoring the helical structure.

2.4 Visible Light Generation

- The opposing rotational flows around the Gluon Balls interact dynamically to produce **visible light**.
- The frequency of the flows corresponds to the wavelength of the emitted light.
- In the context of visible light, the Gluon Balls act dynamically to direct and stabilize the energy flows, ensuring the coherence and propagation of the photon as a structured entity.

Figure 1: Front and lateral views of the YasudaK Photon Model. The red and blue flows represent clockwise and counterclockwise rotations, respectively, stabilized by the central Gluon Balls.

3 Visualization

4 Mathematical Representation

The helicoidal flows can be described by parametric equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x(t) &= r \cos(\omega t + \phi), \\
 y(t) &= r \sin(\omega t + \phi), \\
 z(t) &= vt,
 \end{aligned}$$

where:

- r : Radius of the helicoid.
- ω : Angular frequency of the flow.
- ϕ : Phase offset.
- v : Propagation velocity along the central axis.

The interaction between clockwise and counterclockwise flows is modeled as:

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^{16} (-1)^i E_i \cos(\omega_i t + \phi_i), \quad (1)$$

where E_i represents the energy amplitude of each flow.

5 Gamma-Ray Emission Under Extreme Conditions

While the YasudaK Photon Model focuses on visible light, the Gluon Balls, under extreme conditions such as high-energy collisions or external perturbations, may destabilize and release their stored energy. This process results in the emission of high-energy photons in the gamma-ray spectrum. In such scenarios, the rupture of the Gluon Balls could also generate additional particles, as observed in real experimental phenomena. For instance, gamma-ray bursts or particle showers in high-energy physics experiments may involve similar mechanisms where destabilized Gluon Balls release their stored energy into both radiation and matter. However, such events are rare and do not occur during normal visible light emission.

6 Conclusion

The YasudaK Photon Model offers a structural perspective on the photon, emphasizing the role of energy flows and Gluon Balls in generating visible light. In the context of visible light, Gluon Balls act dynamically to stabilize and direct the energy flows, ensuring the structured coherence of the photon. Under extreme conditions, these same Gluon Balls may rupture, leading to the release of gamma radiation and the generation of particles, aligning with observations from high-energy physics experiments. This framework invites further exploration into the dynamic and quantum properties of light.